

Table 1. Effect of mixed inoculation with compatible and incompatible BI races on lesion number, lesion length, and blast score. Hangzhou, China. ^a

Incompatible race (x 10 ⁵)	Compatible race (x 10 ⁵)	Lesions (no.)	Lesion length (mm)	Blast score ^b
1	0	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
1	1	12.9 (38)	0.97 (45)	3.8 (58)
2	1	10.7 (32)	0.90 (42)	3.4 (52)
4	1	8.3 (25)	0.68 (32)	2.6 (40)
8	1	8.1 (24)	0.73 (34)	2.4 (37)
16	1	8.2 (24)	0.66 (31)	2.6 (40)
0	1	33.6 (100)	2.15 (100)	6.5 (100)

^aFigures in parentheses are percentages relative to the positive check. ^bBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale of 0-9.

Table 2. Pathogenic reactions in interval inoculation with compatible and incompatible races. Hangzhou, China.^a

Incompatible race	Compatible race	Interval (d)	Lesions (no.)	Lesion length (mm)	Blast score ^b
ZA63	0	1	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
ZA63	ZB1	1	20.2 (105)	0.72 (82)	4.3 (81)
0	ZB1	1	19.3 (100)	0.88 (100)	5.3 (100)
ZA63	0	2	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
ZA63	ZB1	2	15.8 (86)	0.47 (57)	3.3 (69)
0	ZB1	2	18.4 (100)	0.83 (100)	4.8 (100)
ZA63	0	3	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
ZA63	ZB1	3	12.5 (84)	0.65 (79)	3.8 (95)
0	ZB1	3	14.8 (100)	0.82 (100)	4.0 (100)

^aFigures in parentheses are percentages relative to the positive check. ^bBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale of 0-9.

Pest resistance—insects

Evaluation of leaf and panicle blast (BI) in lines distributed by CIAT to national programs in Latin America

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Developing germplasm with a high level of BI resistance is one of the major objectives of CIAT's rice program. Lines are evaluated and selected in a disease-prone area, the Santa Rosa Experimental Station in Villavicencio, Colombia (333 m elevation, 4° N, 73° W on alluvial soils). This germplasm is distributed mainly to national partners in the region through the International

Distribution of leaf and panicle blast reactions obtained from VIOAL nurseries from 1985 to 1989 in Latin America. Number of lines evaluated is in the bars. Different letters on top of the bars indicate statistical differences at 5% level using DMRT. SES = *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Observational Nursery for Latin America (VIOAL), organized by the International Network for the Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER).

We conducted a trial to evaluate the 638 CIAT lines included in the VIOAL nurseries from 1985 to 1989.

The experiment was laid out in an augmented design with 11 blocks and checks Ceysvoni, CICA8, Metica 1, Oryzica 1, and Oryzica Llanos 4 planted twice, 15 d apart.

Leaf and panicle BI were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Three evaluations per line were made for leaf BI at 35, 45, and 55 d after planting. The highest score observed was used to characterize the material's reaction.

Panicle BI data were taken on 20 samples in each line. Panicles rating 25 were classified as susceptible and 53 as resistant. The percentage of susceptibility for each line was calculated as the number of panicles classified as susceptible divided by the sample size, multiplied by 100. Data were averaged per year to represent the percentage of mean reaction of the VIOAL.

The results indicate that CIAT seems to be producing lines with more resistance to leaf BI (see figure). The major improvement in resistance to date was between 1985 and 1986. The level of resistance to panicle BI increased in 1986 and has remained at the same level since then. The results suggest that CIAT's breeding approach has resulted in lines with improved BI resistance. □

